

THE VANISHING POINT PROBABILITIES OF SELF_REFERENCING COPIES

by Kyle MacLean Smith on February 29, 2020

Errors in duplication can be remedied to arbitrary accuracy if noise remains less than 50%.¹

Given $c = a*x + b$ asymmetry, The Pythagorean Theorem $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$ is also $a^2 + b^2 = (a*x + b)^2$.

Conjectures

- Given i integers from 1 to Infinity, the sum of $(a, 2*b)*x^{i++}$ approaches $(a, a*x)$.
- Given $x = n/m$, $\{ a = 2*m*n, b = (a/x - a*x)/2 \}$.

Example 1 of 2

Suppose a test for a dangerous pathogen is 90% accurate. If a person gets a test done every 5 years, it is more likely the test will return a false positive after the 25 year mark.

{ test1: year0, test2: year5, test3: year10, test4: year15, test5: year20, test6: year25 }.

{ $(9/10)^6 = 0.531441$, $(9/10)^7 = 0.4782969$ }.

Given { $n = 9, m = 10$ }, { $x = 9/10, a = 180, b = 19, c = 181$ }.

¹ Ray Kurzweil describing Claude Shannon's Information Theory in John von Neumann, *The Computer & The Brain*, Yale University Press, New Haven & London, 2012, page xv.

Example 2 of 2

For most years, there are 365 days in the year. Given at least 23 people, it is more likely than not that 2 people share a birthday even though the probability that 2 people share a birthday is only 1 in 365.

Given { $n = 365 - 1$, $m = 365$ }, { $x = 364/365$, $a = 265720$, $b = 729$, $c = 265721$ }.

Rearrange $a^2 + b^2 = (a*x + b)^2$ to $a = (a*x + 2*b)*x$ and add a degree modifier for $a = (a*x + 2*b)*x^{y-1}$.

Given { $a = 1$, $b = 253$, $y = -1$ }, $x =$ either 23 or -22.

This result matches the $n*(n+1)/2$ triangular number $22*23/2 = 253$ for 22 pairs of 23 people.

$22+21+20+19+18+17+16+15+14+13+12+11+10+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1+0 = 253$.

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